

1 **NOD2, like STING1, is silent in embryonic stem cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here silencing of NOD2
9 during lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Nigro, G., Rossi, R., Commere, P.H., Jay, P. and Sansonetti, P.J., 2014. The cytosolic bacterial
12 peptidoglycan sensor Nod2 affords stem cell protection and links microbes to gut epithelial regeneration.
13 Cell host & microbe, 15(6), pp.792-798.